

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

APP

(amyloid beta precursor protein)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	351 / 05067
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Jesse Wiley ¹ , Gregory Cary ² , YCharOS ³ , and the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center
Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
Document version	1.0
Document version date	February 2024
Citation	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10694525
Affiliations	¹ Sage Bionetworks, Seattle, WA, USA ² The Jackson Laboratory, Bar Harbor, ME, USA ³ University of Montreal, Montreal, Canada

USEFUL LINKS

TREAT-AD

[Visit TREAT-AD](#)

Learn more about the TREAT-AD centers and mission

Agora

[Visit Agora](#)

View Alzheimer's disease target results explorer

AD Knowledge Portal

[Visit AD Knowledge Portal](#)

View available target enabling resources

CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic target analysis: Target Source & Hypothesis

Validated antibodies & generic knockout cell lines: YCharOS antibody characterization report

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 4.71 (rank #2, 100th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of

the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 4.71 out of 5 (rank #2, 100th percentile). The individual score components include 2.73 of 3 for genetics, and 1.98 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of APP RNA is significantly decreased, while APP protein is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. APOE is annotated to GO terms from 15 different biodomains, but primarily terms from the Synapse, Immune

Response, Proteostasis, Lipid Metabolism, Apoptosis, Endolysosome, and APP Metabolism biological domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's

Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no

dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. These data indicate that APP is confidently expressed in all cell types measured in this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

The amyloid beta precursor protein (APP) is one of the hallmark genes associated with Alzheimer's disease (AD)(1). As noted below, APP is a transmembrane protein that is sequentially cleaved by a class of proteases called secretases (2). Mutations adjacent to the gamma-secretase cleavage sites cause a dominantly inherited form of AD (DIAD), which is also often referred to as autosomal dominant AD (ADAD),

early onset AD (EOAD) or familial AD (FAD)(3). APP emerged within the deep proteomic studies as a participant in Module 42 (M42), one of the core modules strongly associated with both cognitive decline and pathological progression in TREAT-AD investigations (4). As noted below, proteolytic processing of APP produces the amyloid peptide, definitional for AD type dementia (2). This project hopes to facilitate the investigation into APP's role in AD pathology through the development or identification of high-quality antibodies, purified proteins, and bioinformatic resources as part of the TREAT-AD target enabling package (TEP) which will be shared with the scientific community.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

The amyloid beta precursor protein (APP) is a single pass type I transmembrane protein with a large extracellular domain and a short intracellular region that binds the transcriptional regulatory complex APBB1/Kat5(5-8). The extracellular region contains the proteolytic cleavage sites for the alpha- and beta-secretases that are involved in alternative cleavage of APP and enabling the remaining membrane resident fragment to enter the proteolytic core the heterotetrameric gamma-secretase complex (9, 10). Gamma-secretase cleaves APP within the transmembrane region, first immediately adjacent to the cytosolic face, and then subsequently trims approximately once per turn of the alpha-helical transmembrane domain (corresponding to every 3 amino acids) (11). APP cleavage by beta-secretase (BACE) and gamma-secretase results in the amyloid peptides, that is characteristic of Alzheimer's disease (AD). There are two closely related paralogous genes in the APP family, APLP1 and APLP2(12). This gene family is critical for embryonic development, as a genetic deletion of two of the three members results in embryonic lethality in mice (12), and forebrain deletion of all three results in severe synaptic deficits and learning impairment (13).

The biological function of APP is not entirely clear, but APP knockout mice demonstrate alterations in synaptic activity, and neuronal cultures derived from the transgenic APP knockout mice demonstrate deficits in the number of observed synapses, suggestive of a role in synapse formation or maintenance (13). The extracellular moiety of APP, liberated by alpha-secretase cleavage of the holoprotein, is reported to have trophic effects on neuronal survival, potentially through the regulation of GABAergic or glutamatergic channel activity (14-16). The small fragment between the alpha- and gamma-cleavage sites is not known to possess any biological activity. The cleavage product resulting from the beta- and gamma-cleavage sites produces the amyloid beta peptide species that aggregate into the oligomers, fibrils, and plaques characteristic of AD pathology (3). A series of mutations adjacent to the beta- or gamma-secretase cleavage sites are associated with the dominantly inherited AD (3), suggesting a strong genetic association between APP and AD.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for APP. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for APP by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of APP in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

References

1. Andrews SJ, Renton AE, Fulton-Howard B, Podlesny-Drabiniok A, Marcora E, Goate AM. The complex genetic architecture of Alzheimer's disease: novel insights and future directions. *EBioMedicine*. 2023;90:104511.
2. Jack CR, Jr., Bennett DA, Blennow K, Carrillo MC, Dunn B, Haeberlein SB, et al. NIA-AA Research Framework: Toward a biological definition of Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2018;14(4):535-62.
3. Knopman DS, Amieva H, Petersen RC, Chételat G, Holtzman DM, Hyman BT, et al. Alzheimer disease. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*. 2021;7(1):33.
4. Johnson ECB, Carter EK, Dammer EB, Duong DM, Gerasimov ES, Liu Y, et al. Large-scale deep multi-layer analysis of Alzheimer's disease brain reveals strong proteomic disease-related changes not observed at the RNA level. *Nat Neurosci*. 2022;25(2):213-25.
5. Probst S, Krüger M, Kägi L, Thöni S, Schuppli D, Nitsch RM, et al. Fe65 is the sole member of its family that mediates transcription regulated by the amyloid precursor protein. *J Cell Sci*. 2020;133(17).
6. Gersbacher MT, Goodger ZV, Trutzel A, Bundschuh D, Nitsch RM, Konietzko U. Turnover of amyloid precursor protein family members determines their nuclear signaling capability. *PLoS One*. 2013;8(7):e69363.
7. von Rotz RC, Kohli BM, Bosset J, Meier M, Suzuki T, Nitsch RM, et al. The APP intracellular domain forms nuclear multiprotein complexes and regulates the transcription of its own precursor. *J Cell Sci*. 2004;117(Pt 19):4435-48.
8. Cao X, Sudhof TC. A transcriptionally [correction of transcriptively] active complex of APP with Fe65 and histone acetyltransferase Tip60. *Science*. 2001;293(5527):115-20.
9. Wolfe MS. Unraveling the complexity of γ -secretase. *Semin Cell Dev Biol*. 2020;105:3-11.
10. Wolfe MS. Dysfunctional γ -Secretase in Familial Alzheimer's Disease. *Neurochem Res*. 2019;44(1):5-11.
11. Devkota S, Williams TD, Wolfe MS. Familial Alzheimer's disease mutations in amyloid protein precursor alter proteolysis by γ -secretase to increase amyloid β -peptides of ≥ 45 residues. *J Biol Chem*. 2021;296:100281.
12. Müller UC, Zheng H. Physiological functions of APP family proteins. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med*. 2012;2(2):a006288.
13. Steubler V, Erdinger S, Back MK, Ludewig S, Fässler D, Richter M, et al. Loss of all three APP family members during development impairs synaptic function and plasticity, disrupts learning, and causes an autism-like phenotype. *The EMBO Journal*. 2021;40(12):e107471.

14. Rice HC, Marcassa G, Chrysidou I, Horr K, Young-Pearse TL, Mller UC, et al. Contribution of GABAergic interneurons to amyloid- β plaque pathology in an APP knock-in mouse model. *Mol Neurodegener.* 2020;15(1):3.
15. Rice HC, de Malmazet D, Schreurs A, Frere S, Van Molle I, Volkov AN, et al. Secreted amyloid- β precursor protein functions as a GABA(B)R1a ligand to modulate synaptic transmission. *Science.* 2019;363(6423).
16. Yao W, Tambini MD, Liu X, D'Adamio L. Tuning of Glutamate, But Not GABA, Release by an Intrasynaptic Vesicle APP Domain Whose Function Can Be Modulated by β - or α -Secretase Cleavage. *J Neurosci.* 2019;39(35):6992-7005.

We respectfully request that this document is cited using the DOI value as given above if the content is used in your work.